

Simultaneous Estimation of Isoniazid, Metformin Hydrochloride and Glimepiride by RP-HPLC

Sawant Ramesh L¹, Tanpure Kallyani D^{1*}, Bharat Anjali V¹, Jadhav Kallyani A¹

Abstract: Rapid RP-HPLC method was developed for simultaneous estimation of isoniazid, metformin hydrochloride and glimepiride. Analysis was done in synthetic mixture of isoniazid, metformin and glimepiride. Stationary phase as Hibar® 250-4.6 HPLC column Purosphen® STAR RP-18. Mobile phase methanol:water at the ratio 70:30 v/v was used. Flow rate was 0.8 ml/min, wavelength was set as 234 nm and the volume of inject was 100 ppm. The retention time of the isoniazid, metformin HCl and glimepiride was found to be 2.88, 2.41 and 4.66 minutes respectively.

INTRODUCTION

Isoniazid, metformin hydrochloride and glimepiride plays vital role in the treatment of patient suffering individual diseases such as diabetes and tuberculosis. Hence there is no method developed for the simultaneous estimation of isoniazid (antituberculosis) and metformin hydrochloride, glimepiride (antidiabetic) drugs in combination. Simultaneous estimation of isoniazid, metformin hydrochloride and glimepiride done by separation using chromatographic method like HPLC, which simpler, economic and effective method for simultaneous estimation of isoniazid (antituberculosis) and metformin hydrochloride, glimepiride (antidiabetic) drugs in synthetic mixture.

Isoniazid (pyridine-4-carbohydrazid) hetrocyclic compound which first line drug used in tuberculosis. It is effective both in acidic and alkaline medium. Isoniazid is tuberculocidal for rapidly multiplying bacilli but static for increasing resting bacilli. INH inhibits the synthesis of mycolic acid which is important component of the mycobacterial cell wall by which it shows tuberculocidal action.

Metformin hydrochloride (MET) (N,N-dimethylimidodicarbonimidic diamide hydrochloride) is a biguanide antihyperglycemic agent used for treating non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus. It improves glycemic production, decreasing glucose absorption and increasing insulin mediated glucose uptake. Metformin is an oral antihyperglycemic agent that improves glucose tolerance in patient with NIDDM lowering both basal and postprandial plasma glucose.

Glimepiride (GLP)1-{{p-[2-(3-ethyl-4-methyl-2-oxo-3-pyrroline-1-carboxamide)ethyl]-phenyl]-sulfonyl}-3-(trans-4-methyl cyclohexyl)urea. It is used to treat type II diabetes in which body close does not use insulin normally and therefore, cannot control the amount of sugar in the blood. GLP lowers the body sugar by causing the pancreas to produce insulin. [1-9]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

HPLC grade methanol, double distilled water was used which is self generated from triple distillation glass

¹Pd. Dr. Vithalrao Vikhe Patil Foundation's, College of Pharmacy, Viladghat, Ahmednagar- 414111, Maharashtra, India.

E-mail: tanpurekalyani@gmail.com

*Corresponding author

assembly. Isoniazid, metformin hydrochloride and glimepiride bulk drugs sample. HPLC system (PU2080HPLC2000, JASCO, Power requirement: 230V, 50Hz) with Jasco PU-2080 Plus (intelligent HPLC Pump), Jasco UV-2075 Plus Intelligent UV/Vis detector with column was employed. BROWIN CHROMATOGRAPHY SOFTWARE was used for data acquisition and processing.

Analytical Column

HiQ sil C18 HS size 4.6 mm inner diameter 250 mm length, No. OH500218

Determination of Appropriate UV Wavelength

The appropriate wavelength for the detection of the drug in mobile phase was determined by wavelength scanning over the range of 200-400 nm. After scanning appropriate wavelength was selected

Chromatographic Condition

The mobile phase was prepared by using methanol and water in the ratio 70:30 v/v wavelength was set at 234 nm. This wavelength was selected because it was UV maximum and provides the sensitivity needed for quantitation of the low drug concentration in synthetic mixture. The column temperature was maintained at room temperature. The mobile phase was pumped at flow rate 0.8 ml/min with 20 µl injection volume.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Wavelength Selection

The ultraviolet spectra of isoniazid (Figure 2) metformin hydrochloride (Figure 3) and glimepiride (Figure 4) showed at 260 nm, 234 and 230 nm respectively. Therefore, 234 nm wavelength was selected to achieve the highest sensitivity for the study.

Selection of Mobile Phase

Different combinations of methanol and water were tested and the optimum condition at methanol-water (70:30 v/v). The obtained chromatograph showed a retention time for isoniazid 2.05 min (Figure 5 and Table 1), metformin hydrochloride 1.76 min (Figure 6 and Table 2) and glimepiride 4.67 min (Figure 7 and Table 3) for metformin hydrochloride respectively. In the synthetic mixture of isoniazid, metformin hydrochloride and glimepiride shows rapid separation with retention time 2.411, 2.88 and 4.665 respectively (Figure 8 and Table 4).

Figure 1a: Structure of isoniazid

Figure 1b: Structure of metformin hydrochloride

Figure 1c: Structure of glimepiride

Figure 2: Spectra of isoniazid API

Figure 3: Spectra of metformin hydrochloride API

Figure 4: Spectra of glimepiride API

Figure 5: Chromatogram of isoniazid sample using RP-HPLC at $\lambda_{\max} = 234$ nm

Figure 6: Chromatogram of metformin hydrochloride sample using RP-HPLC at $\lambda_{\max} = 234$ nm

Figure 7: Chromatogram of glimepiride sample using RP-HPLC at $\lambda_{\max} = 234$ nm

Selection of HPLC Stationary Phase

The best results were obtained by using Hibar^R 250-4.6 HPLC column Purosphens^R STAR RP-18 as compared to other different stationary phase.

CONCLUSION

The analytical method by RP-HPLC is rapid, sensible, economic simultaneous determination of antituberculosis and antidiabetics bulk drugs in synthetic mixture. The

optimum parameters that can be used as follows; Two solvents are used that are methanol, double graded distilled water which degassed having ratio 70:30 v/v. Wavelength was set at 234 nm. The mobile phase was pumped at flow rate 0.8 ml/min with 20 μ l injection volume. Hence it can be concluded that the developed RP-HPLC method is employed successfully for the estimation of isoniazid, metformin hydrochloride and glimepiride in synthetic mixture.

Figure 8: Chromatogram of synthetic mixture of isoniazid, metformin hydrochloride and glimepiride using RP-HPLC at $\lambda_{\max} = 234 \text{ nm}$

Table 1: Chromatographic Data for Isoniazid

Name	RT (min)	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{Sec}$)	Resolution	Plates	Asymmetry
Isoniazid	2.05	4212109	0.00	3213	1.61

Total Area of Peak = 4212109 [$\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{Sec}$]

Table 2: Chromatographic Data for Metformin Hydrochloride

Name	RT (min)	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{Sec}$)	Resolution	Plates	Asymmetry
Metformin hydrochloride	1.765	2785767	0.00	3808	1.60

Total Area of Peak = 2785767 [$\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{Sec}$]

Table 3: Chromatographic Data for Glimepiride

Name	RT (min)	Area [$\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{Sec}$]	Resolution	Plates	Asymmetry
Glimepiride	4.674	1726434	0.00	2761	1.72

Total Area of Peak = 1726434 [$\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{Sec}$]

Table 4: Chromatographic data for Isoniazid, Metformin Hydrochloride and Glimepiride

Name	RT (min)	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{Sec}$)	Resolution	Plates	Asymmetry
Isoniazid	2.411	6451752	1.71	2309	1.35
Metformin hydrochloride	2.881	5443131	3.65	3769	1.37
Glimepiride	4.665	1385185	2.33	7493	1.43

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